

GEN

GENDER & DIVERSITY INDEX

EXECUTIVE
SUMMARY
2025

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Funded by
the European Union

INTRODUCTION

Women remain underrepresented in deep tech, particularly in leadership and share of investment. This is not just a question of equity- it limits innovation and economic growth. Despite some progress in education and entrepreneurship, gender disparities persist, particularly when it comes to raising funds.

Working closely with the European Innovation Council and our Board of Experts, we have created a Gender & Diversity Index to track and drive change in Europe's deep tech ecosystem. decisions.

The report provides a dashboard of indicators, identifying key barriers and highlighting actionable insights to remove bias, intentional or otherwise, from investment

Analysing existing and new data, across three interlinked tiers that lead to impact, our report explores whether there are gaps in the deep tech landscape, when they emerge and whether they continue to exist throughout the investment journey.

Spoiler alert: yes, there are gaps; yes, they get worse as start-ups scale; and yes, we can take action to unlock an extra EUR 181 billion for the European economy.

DEEP TECH TALENT

The supply of the talent behind our deep tech founders. STEM and research roles.

INTELLECTUAL & SOCIAL CAPITAL

Access to network and intellectual assets that are the basis of deep tech companies.

ASSET & INVESTMENT

Investment raised and value generated by women-led companies in deep-tech.

DATA SOURCES

The Gender & Diversity index was created using a mixed-methods approach, gathering most data from existing reputable secondary sources. Primary data sources were collected when there were evident data gaps.

The primary data collected include the GENDEX survey with 150 diverse founders from the EU 26+ UK, interviews with 20 women founders and further interviews with deep tech investors.

The secondary data collected included public statistical data sets, proprietary databases from specialist companies and desk research.

[*https://eurogendex.org/3d-flip-book/gendex-data-analysis-of-the-gender-diversity-scorecard/](https://eurogendex.org/3d-flip-book/gendex-data-analysis-of-the-gender-diversity-scorecard/)

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1.

KEY FINDINGS

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KEY FINDINGS

THERE IS A LACK OF DIVERSITY IN THE DEEP TECH SECTORS TARGETED BY THE EIC.

By addressing the structural imbalances within the deep tech ecosystem, we can create a more equitable environment where women-led companies have greater access to EIC funding and deliver greater returns for the European innovation ecosystem..

LOWER DIVERSITY AT EARLIER STAGES OF THE PIPELINE HAS AN IMPACT ON INVESTMENT OUTCOMES.

Data showed that whilst **42% of STEM graduates are women**, their representation narrows significantly at leadership levels, with only **20-25% holding STEM chair positions in top-tier institutions**. Closing this gap through targeted initiatives can unlock untapped potential and build a more inclusive deep tech ecosystem.

KEY FINDINGS

EVEN WHEN INVESTMENT IS SECURED, WOMEN RECEIVE LESS FAVOURABLE TERMS THAN THOSE OFFERED TO MEN.

Women-led companies tend to have lower burn rates than men-led companies in the pre-seed and seed stages, likely due to greater fundraising challenges that encourage more efficient spending. However, at later stages, men-led companies tend to outperform women-led ones in burn rate efficiency. Moreover, during tougher investment periods, **the proportion of down rounds is mostly equal between women- and men-led companies.**

THE INVESTMENT GAP BETWEEN WOMEN AND MEN HIGHLIGHTS AN OPPORTUNITY TO EXPAND THE DEEP TECH FOUNDER POOL.

Some data points (valuations at non-IPO and IPO exits) suggest better outcomes for women-led companies. **Women-led companies provided just over 11% of the value raised at non-IPO exits**, despite accounting for only 0.6% of the total number of non-IPO exits. Closing the gap between women and men-led companies or increasing support for **women-led businesses could unlock value of €181 billion.**

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**DEEP TECH
TALENT TIER**

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DEEP TECH TALENT TIER

42%

The proportion of women STEM graduates in the European union is 42%.

41%

Of the workforce of scientists and engineers in both the public and private sectors in 2022.

ACADEMIA AND RESEARCH ARE THE MOST COMMON CAREER PATHS FOR FOUNDERS;

60% of men founders had experience in these fields, compared to just 45% of women founders.

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Under 1 in 5 graduates in **deep tech disciplines most closely** related to the creation of scalable start-ups - engineering and ICT- are women.

Only 20–25% of academic leadership positions in leading European universities are occupied by women.

Across the EU, only 1 in 3 researchers is a woman. At current growth rates, it **would take it would take 19–21 years to achieve gender parity in STEM research .**

DEEP TECH TALENT TIER

SHARE OF WOMEN GRADUATES IN STEM

Year: 2022

Source: Source:GENDEX elaboration on Eurostat, Distribution of male and female graduates in different fields of education, by education level and programme orientation [educ_uoe_grad10], October 2024 • Created with Datawrapper

Despite ongoing initiatives since 2019 to boost growth in science and technology, data shows little progress. Participation in fields like physics and engineering remains low.

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**INTELLECTUAL &
SOCIAL CAPITAL TIER**

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INTELLECTUAL & SOCIAL CAPITAL TIER

22%

From 2014 to 2024, the share of women-led deep tech companies remained at 22% of the total.

12 MONTHS

On average it takes women led start-ups over 12 months to receive their first term sheet compared to 7 months for men.

WOMEN FOUNDERS ARE REROUTING AROUND BIAS IN INVESTMENT

Women founders' concerns about bias, discrimination, or harassment within the investment ecosystem often drive them to pursue alternative paths to grow their businesses.

Research shows that **women founders in deep tech own less intellectual property rights** than their male counterparts.

Women founders in deep tech are more likely to **develop intellectual property independently** rather than transferring it from previous companies or research institutions.

Women founders' experiences and concerns about potential bias, discrimination or harassment in the investment ecosystem lead women to **seek alternative routes.**

INTELLECTUAL & SOCIAL CAPITAL TIER

SHARE OF WOMEN EMPLOYED BY THE MAGNIFICENT 7 IN 2024 (EST)

Source: Microsoft annual company report; GENDEX estimations on Amazon annual company report; GENDEX estimations on a sample of at least 1,000 European employees' profiles on LinkedIn for the other companies

SHARE OF WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TOP EUROPEAN TECH UNICORNS IN 2024 (EST)

Source: Relex annual company report; GENDEX estimations on a sample of at least 1,000 European employees' profile on LinkedIn for the other companies

INTELLECTUAL & SOCIAL CAPITAL TIER

SHARE OF DEEP TECH COMPANIES WITH AT LEAST ONE WOMAN IN A POSITION AS A KEY EXECUTIVE BOARD MEMBER BY DOMAIN

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N= 20,000) and Dealroom (N= 8,000)

Within European deep tech, biotechnologies, robotics and autonomous systems and quantum technologies currently have the highest proportion of women-led companies.

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**ASSET &
INVESTMENT TIER**

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ASSET & INVESTMENT TIER

Although the IPO rate for men-led companies was ten times higher than that of women-led companies.

34%

Women-led companies had a 34% higher valuation at IPO than men-led companies.

WOMEN-LED FIRMS OUTPERFORM IN KEY SECTORS

Women-led companies raise fewer rounds and reach unicorn status more slowly, yet they outperform in IPO valuations and show strong results in biotech.

Women led companies close one deal for every three closed by men led companies

Women-led companies are more likely to have a **higher share of closed rounds in biotechnology** than to men led companies.

Women led companies are more likely to **take six years to reach unicorn status** compared to the average of five years for men led companies.

INVESTMENT RAISED BY WOMEN-LED COMPANIES

Source: GENDEX analysis on a sample of a total EU+UK of around N=20,000 companies from PitchBook and N= around 8,000 companies from Dealroom

The total amount of investment raised by women-led and men-led companies in the EU27+UK highlight a persistent funding gap, with women-led companies securing significantly less capital despite an increasing share of funding rounds in recent years.

N° AND SHARE OF NON-IPO EXITS FOR WOMEN-LED COMPARED TO MEN

Source: GENDEX analysis of a Dealroom sample (N = 1,300) of EU and UK companies acquired, merged and/or bought out

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DEEP TECH INVESTORS

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INVESTORS

The percentage of **investments going to women-led companies decreased from 2014 to 2024**, but **the actual number of companies receiving funding increased over the same period.**

GENDER DISPARITIES PERSIST WITHIN EUROPEAN INVESTMENT FIRMS

Despite studies indicating that funds managed by a greater number of women leaders tend to yield higher returns, gender disparities persist within European investment firms.

Research shows that biases influence decisions; **pitches presented by men founders are favoured over those from women**, even if the content of the pitch is the same.

Funds with the largest AUM (from €1 billion to over €5 billion) almost always have **at least one woman making investment decisions.**

ASSETS UNDER MANAGEMENT IN VENTURE CAPITAL FUNDS WITH AT LEAST ONE WOMAN DECISION MAKER

Source: PitchBook, October 2024, N= around 350 VC, PE and Family Offices firms, with yearly fluctuations

Despite an increase in the participation of women in leadership positions across investment firms, the proportion of women in leadership roles has remained constant for VC and has even decreased in Private Equity

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**RECOMMENDATIONS
FOR STAKEHOLDERS**

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RECOMMENDATIONS FOR STAKEHOLDERS

FOR POLICYMAKERS

IMPROVE DATA COLLECTION

Existing data on STEM education and early investment stages lack key gender-specific insights, such as IP ownership and funding distribution. The European Patent Office should systematically record gender data. While mandatory data collection is costly, voluntary disclosure and standardised reporting can help investors analyse and address diversity gaps. Encouraging transparency - without excessive regulation - supports informed decision-making.

STRENGTHEN IP SUPPORT

IP is at the heart of all deep tech companies. Supporting women in protecting and commercialising their IP through targeted training, financial aid, and legal assistance can help level the playing field. Private initiatives like She Invents offer models for ensuring women's innovations are protected and viable

USE PUBLIC INVESTMENT TO DRIVE CHANGE

Women founders face barriers that affect funding access, yet those who secure investment often outperform. Public funds can promote gender equity by requiring co-investment partners to demonstrate efforts toward increasing women's participation or at the very least proving there is no bias. Additional measures include training investors to recognise bias, expanding networking opportunities for women founders - not women only networks- and scaling mentorship programmes.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR STAKEHOLDERS

FOR INVESTORS

REFRAME THE NARRATIVE

Underfunding women-led deep tech companies is not just a gender issue but a missed financial opportunity. Data show that women-led companies can deliver strong returns yet remain systematically underfunded. Showcasing success stories with clear financial metrics could help reverse perceptions that women do not have what it takes.

REDUCE BIAS IN INVESTMENT DECISIONS

Bias, conscious or unconscious, affects investment choices. Structured assessments and blind reviews can help focus on business merit rather than founder identity. Clear evaluation frameworks reduce similarity bias, ensuring diverse strengths are recognised.

INCREASE DIVERSITY IN INVESTMENT COMMITTEES

A more diverse investment team broadens perspectives and enhances decision-making. Including more women in key roles increases the likelihood of identifying overlooked opportunities and challenging entrenched biases.

CALL OUT BIAS

Women founders report differential treatment and find themselves in positions in which they are talked down too. Investors and other stakeholders must recognise and address this behaviour when it occurs to signal that it is not acceptable.

GENDEX

<https://eurogendex.org/resources/>

Explore key findings & uncover where gaps remain in gender inclusion across Europe's deep tech landscape.

ARE YOU AN INVESTOR?

Benchmark your firm's performance against your peers to find out whether you might have a problem with hidden bias.

Your inputs are confidential and will only be used provide the aggregated benchmark.

<Data.eurogendex.org/gendex-pulse/>